

Overseas Filipino Workers' Employment Compliance, Difficulties, and Job Satisfaction in the Middle East

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Abstract:

This study aimed to determine the extent of OFWs' employment compliance, level of difficulties, and level of job satisfaction in the Middle East during the last quarter of the Calendar Year 2022. A quantitative research design was applied. It was conducted in a District of GCC in the Middle East. The 100 respondents from the two Occupational Classifications (Professionals and Non-professionals) of the four (4) private Organizational Groups of OFWs' answered the Survey Questionnaire paper-based. Content areas cover staff qualification, government requirements, contract requirements, life experience abroad, accommodation, transportation, safety, working hours and working conditions, compensation, benefits, job security and tenure, recognition, reward, promotions, and professional development opportunities. The data collection was gathered with permission from the group leaders. Statistical tools were processed through SPSS. Frequency count was used for profiling, Mann-Whitney U Test was used for Comparative analysis, and Spearman rho Test was used for nonparametric correlational analysis. The extent of the OFWs' Employment Compliance in relation to the level of Difficulties was significant. The extent of employment compliance in relation to the level of Job Satisfaction was significant. And the level of the Difficulties in relation to Job Satisfaction was significant. Dependent and Independent variables rely on each other as part of a whole package for OFWs' working in the Middle East.

Keywords: OFW, Middle East, Employment Compliance, Difficulties, Job Satisfaction

Introduction:

Background of the Study

The figure of Filipino worker is ubiquitous globally (Tungohan, 2021). This is related to Filipino migration and diaspora. According to Pacoma (2020), "Diaspora is not a new concept for Filipinos; they have been constantly connected to migration, one of the interconnected aspects of the global workforce. Diaspora and migration as common household terms can be traced back from the first Overseas Filipino farmworkers in Hawaii in the middle of 1900s to the present relocated skilled workers and domestic helpers in the Middle East and various Asian countries."

A migrant worker is a concept for Overseas Filipino Workers (OFWs); it is a term for a Filipino employed to work outside the Philippines (Bautista & Tamayo, 2020). They left the country bound with the honor and the love of their families to seek greener pastures (Oakley, 2020). They brought their composure, professionalism, knowledge, skills, and abilities to work abroad (Al-Seghayer, 2017). They were obliged to follow the government laws in the respective countries they deployed; required to follow the organization's policies and procedures (Safa et al., 2016), and adopt the culture and lifestyle (Mandolfo, 2019) of the country they served to sustain life abroad (McLaughlin, 2020). The adoption of the term OFW was formerly called Overseas Contract Workers (OCWs).

The word "Filipino" replaced "Contract" to give honor to our countrymen called "Heroes of the New Millennium" (Bautista & Tamayo, 2020). The Philippine government was committed to securing OFWs' welfare through Philippine Consulates in their respective countries of deployment. It was concretized by R.A. 8042, the "Migrant Workers and Overseas Filipinos Act of 1995". The R.A. 8042 was amended by R.A. 10022 on 27 July 2010. In 2017, the OFWs' administration under the Philippine Overseas Employment Administration (POEA) was constituted as the Department of Migrant Workers (DMW) through the enactment of R.A. No. 11641, signed on December 30, 2021.

This study dealt with the different facets of migratory challenges among migrants and migrant workers in the Gulf. The Gulf is in the Middle East, currently known as GCC or Gulf Cooperating Council. Nevertheless, "despite the high

numbers of Filipino migrant workers in various parts of the world, little attention has been directed to them in terms of academic discourse" (Pacoma, 2020). Migration constitutes one of the most remarkable geographical regions of the world with respect to labor migration of labor shortage. The surplus labor of foreign workers from other countries, primarily from the Philippines, caused OFWs to move as migrant workers in the Middle East and other part of the world.

The Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA, 2022), OFWs from April to September 2020 is estimated to be 1.77 million worldwide. The Middle East is the leading destination of OFWs. According to Mapa (2020), OFWs' occupations include managers, professionals, technicians, and associated professionals, clerical support, service and sales, skilled agricultural forestry and fishery, craft and related trades, plant and machine operators, assemblers, and elementary occupations.

The current gap in employment compliance, difficulties, and job satisfaction in Middle Eastern countries is the imposition of the rigorous localization program. The program stresses employment for native workers over foreign. Formerly, the workforce in the Middle East was empowered by local men and foreign workers. By contrast, according to Shaya et al. (2017), "the Middle Eastern context, on eliminating gender discrimination and achieving women's empowerment, aimed to develop a conceptual model on the principal social and cultural factors including the success of leadership roles and shaping their leadership style to be transformational."

The difficulties of the expatriates are the new alignment on the advancement of current educational training required. Newly graduated locals are replacing expatriates. The turnover of jobs from expatriates to locals was pursued actively. With that, expatriates were given a leeway notice for repatriation or non-renewal of the contract. The level of difficulties by the expatriates caused anxiety and stress. Furthermore, the implication of this study was aligned with OFWs' current knowledge, skills, and competencies to the global human resources need.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the extent of OFWs' employment compliance, level of difficulties, and level of job satisfaction in the Middle East during the last quarter of the Calendar Year 2022.

Literature Review:

Employment Compliance. According to Budhwar et al. (2019), the Middle Eastern context was a unique and captivating ground for studying and researching International Human Resource Management (IHRM) because of the unique nature of the workforce in this region, predominantly expatriates from different parts of the world. The term Middle East defines as a cultural area that does not have precise borders. A variety of terminologies have been used to denote the region. These vary from "Middle East," "Near East," "Middle East-North Africa (MENA)," "Southwest Asia," "Greater Middle East," "Levant," "Arabian Peninsula" or the "Arab World" in a very general sense, the terms used by both academics and policymakers.

Difficulties. The primary employment difficulties in the Middle East experienced by expatriates were the localization policies. According to Peck (2017), due to rising unemployment, particularly among skilled and professional native youth, localization policies have become increasingly popular in the oil-exporting countries of the Middle East, where quota-based initiatives were now a core government strategy to address native youth unemployment. These policies now exist in all six countries of the GCC: Saudi Arabia, Bahrain, Oman, Kuwait, Qatar, and the United Arab Emirates. These quotas are seen as a crucial tool to address the economic instability caused by high native unemployment. Nitaqat policy in the "Saudization" program of Saudi Arabia was one of the first of these policies to be enforced on a large scale and was unprecedented in the breadth of its scope as well as its rigorous enforcement and close monitoring. The Nitaqat policy is a key test case to measure the potential of these programs to combat unemployment, as well as an important case study for how the costs imposed by such quotas might restrict the growth of targeted firms.

Job satisfaction. The theory of Maslow's 'Hierarchy of Needs' was also supported by the theory of Herzberg's Motivation-Hygiene, also known as the Two Factor theory by Frederick Herzberg. Job satisfaction was theoretically related to these two theories. The individual needs to satisfy every level of needs for him/her to move to the higher or highest level of needs, such as physiological, safety, social, esteem, and self-actualization. Maslow theories magnify that once the needs at one level are satisfied, it ceases to motivate, and the desire shifts to the next level (Amin, 2021).

Employment compliance. Working abroad primarily required a dept understanding of job contracts prior to deployment. The Contract Requirements were supported by (Magliveras, 2019), who stated that "Overseas Filipino Workers are bound by contract to work with a valid working permit visa." OFWs working abroad, according to Ruiz (2014), stated that "exporting surplus Filipino labor alleviated from an oversupply of educated degrees coming from a highly unregulated and autonomous private and other higher government education systems."

Research Methodology:

This section presents the methodology of the study. It discusses the research design, respondents of the study, the data-gathering procedure, which includes the research instrument and the test of its validity and reliability, the analytical schemes, and the statistical tools.

Research Design

This study utilized descriptive, comparative, and relational research design. This design is a scientific method often used as a precursor to quantitative research designs, the general overview giving some valuable pointers as to what variables are worth testing quantitatively (Stone et al., 2021). It aimed to provide facts and scientific judgment of the current situations of the OFWs in the Middle East on employment compliance, difficulties, and job satisfaction. Also, this design is appropriate for the study as it helps reveal patterns and connections that might otherwise go unnoticed, present situations, and determine the prevalent issues making adequate and accurate interpretation of the data gathered from the survey questionnaire.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were taken from the two Occupational Classifications (Professionals and Non-professionals) from the four (4) private Organizational Groups of Overseas Filipino Workers in the district Group A (Health Wellness), Group B (Women's Group), Group C (Men's Sports Group), Group D (Singles'/Couples' Group) drawing a total population of 134. Due to the numerous respondents, sampling was employed using Cochran's Formula to determine the sample randomly and proportionately.

Table 1 shows the distribution of the respondents according to groups.
Distribution of the Respondents

Group	Population (N)	Sample (n)	Percentage (%)
Group A	11	8	8.00
Group B	37	28	28.00
Group C	63	47	47.00
Group D	23	17	17.00
Total	134	100	100.00

Data-Gathering Instrument

The researcher gathered the needed data for this study by constructing a Self-made Likert Scale Survey Questionnaire to determine the extent of Overseas Filipino Workers' employment compliance, level of difficulties, and job satisfaction in the Middle East. The survey was done in a private organization of one District of GCC Country in the Middle East through the cooperation of all group leaders and respondents as well. The questionnaire was divided into 4 Parts. Part 1 consisted of the respondents' profiles in terms of age, sex, occupational classification, skill level, and length of service. Part 2 has 3 areas; each area has five (5) items of measurable factors, A. Employment Compliance as an independent variable with areas as (a.) staff qualification, (b.) government requirements, and (c.) contract requirements. Part 3 has 3 areas; each area has five (5) items of measurable factors, B. Difficulties as the independent variable with areas as (a.) life experience abroad, (b.) accommodation, transportation, and safety, and (c.) working hours and working conditions. And lastly, Part 4 has 3 areas, and each area has five (5) items of measurable factors, C. Job satisfaction as a dependent variable with areas as (a.) compensation, benefits, and job security and tenure, (b.) recognition, reward, and promotions, and (c.) professional development opportunities. Parts 2 - 4 have a total of 45 items of measurable factors. Each item was rated on a scale of 1 - 5, using a 5-point Likert scale rating with 1 - Almost Never (Hindi), 2 - Rarely (Bihira), 3 - Sometimes (Minsan), 4 - Often (Madalas), and 5 - Always (Lagi).

Validity

Validity refers to the fact that a tool measures exactly what it proposes to measure (Chapelle & Lee, 2021). The researcher ensured that the items reflected the desired construct. Hence suggestions and recommendations of the jurors were noted and thoroughly incorporated. As to the appropriateness of the items in the questionnaire, each juror was requested to rate the instrument using the criteria created and presented. Face and content validation was used to validate this study. The survey instrument validation criteria set by Carter V. Good and Douglas E. Scates, with a rating of one (1) as poor and five (5) as excellent, was used in this research. The interpretations are as follows:

Excellent (4.21 – 5.00); Very Good (3.41 - 4.20); Good (2.61 – 3.40); Fair (1.81 – 2.60); Poor (1.00 – 1.80). The consolidated validation by the validators in this study resulted to a 4.89 rating, interpreted as "Excellent."

Reliability

Reliability is the ability to reproduce a consistent result in time and space or from different observers, presenting aspects of a measure's coherence, stability, equivalence, and homogeneity. It is one of the primary quality criteria for an instrument. For reliability instruments, Cronbach's Alpha (α) formula is used for the test to be reliable. Cronbach's alpha (α) coefficient demonstrates the covariance level between the items of a scale. Thus, the lower the sum of items variance is, the more consistent the instrument will be (De Souza et al., 2017).

The reliability index was interpreted using the reliability coefficient interpretation guide as per the verbal description developed by J. P. Guilford. Cronbach's alpha (α) and internal consistency interpretation: the value of $\alpha \geq 0.9$ interpreted as "Excellent," $0.9 > \alpha \geq 0.8$ interpreted as "Good," $0.8 > \alpha \geq 0.7$ interpreted as "Accepted," $0.7 > \alpha \geq 0.6$ interpreted as "Questionable," $0.6 > \alpha \geq 0.5$ interpreted as "Poor," $0.5 > \alpha$ interpreted as "Unacceptable." After measuring the validity of the questionnaire and the incorporation of all corrections and suggestions from the jury and the panel members, the reliability of the instrument was established. Dry-run participants of 30 OFWs in homogenous samples from two stratified occupational classifications in the district are considered a subset sample was chosen for this study. Then, internal consistency using Cronbach's alpha (α) is employed to determine the reliability index of the questionnaire.

A reliability instrument was used Cronbach's Alpha (α) for the test to be reliable. The researcher administered the test once. According to De Souza et al. (2017), to be reliable, the obtained value of the test should be between 0.70 to 1.00 are ideal and reliable. The computed alpha for the Extent of the OFWs' employment compliance is 0.893, interpreted as "Good," for the Level of OFWs' difficulties is 0.927, interpreted as "Excellent," and the Level of OFWs' job satisfaction is 0.893, interpreted as "Good."

Data-Gathering Procedure

The most appropriate data-gathering procedure for this descriptive research design is a paper-based survey questionnaire. The survey questionnaire has a list of questions intended to elicit answers to a given problem in a logical order and not too personal to the respondents (Brace, 2018). Upon the approval of the questionnaire by the panel members, the researcher sought the help of seven (7) validators considered experts in the field of educational management and advanced research for validation. The reliability of the research questionnaire follows administering it to 30 OFWs in one District of the GCC Country in the Middle East, considered a subset of actual respondents.

The computation for the reliability of the survey questionnaire follows, then the researcher conducted the study and began the data gathering. The answered questionnaires by the respondents were gathered, tallied, and tabulated using SPSS, analyzed, and interpreted according to the specific problems outlined in this study. Likewise, the statistical tables and graphs were constructed as per consideration of the objectives stated in the study.

The study was conducted as independent research with no connection to any organizations, agencies, private businesses, or government institutions except the school attended by the researcher. The researcher surveyed a private group of OFWs by seeking permission from the group leaders and a one-on-one approach with the targeted respondents. The researcher explained and addressed the queries of respondents on the confidentiality of personal identity and the purpose of the research. The researcher explained to the respondent individually that the responses provided were kept confidential between the researcher and the respondent only. The questionnaire didn't contain personal information to identify the respondent who answered the questions to avoid conflict of interest.

Research Ethics Protocol

The study was conducted as independent research with no connection to any organizations, agencies, private businesses, or government institutions except the school attended by the researcher. Also, the study budget was provided solely by the researcher.

Ethically, the primary purpose of research should be centered on humans and their conditions. Quantitative research often describes its core production purpose as correct, valid, or unbiased inferences (Zyphur et al., 2017).

To avoid conflict of interest on the side of the researcher and to protect the privacy and integrity of every respondent and the researcher, data were gathered privately with confidentiality between the researcher and the respondents. Permission from the private group leaders and voluntary participation of the respondents with no coercion to participate in the research was secured. To participate in this research study, participants were adequately informed about the research, comprehend the information, and have the freedom of choice, allowing them to decide whether to participate or decline. Participants' agreement to participate in the study was obtained only after a thorough explanation of the research process (Arifin, 2018). A written agreement between the researcher and the respondent was not implemented to avoid tracking and identifying the respondent's personal information.

Almost all research guarantees the participants' confidentiality – they were assured that identifying information will not be made available to anyone who is not directly involved in the study (Trochim, 2021). Confidentiality means that information is restricted to those authorized to have access to it. The strictness of confidentiality normally increases with the degree of sensitivity of the information and the degree of vulnerability of the research subject. In essence, confidentiality in the relationship between the researcher and the research subject is to be regarded as an obligation for the researcher and a right for the research subject (Torp, 2015). Participants were guaranteed that the information they shared would not be disclosed to the public or to anyone for that matter. A strict principle of anonymity essentially means that the participant will remain anonymous throughout the study – even to the researchers themselves (Trochim, 2021).

Ethical standards also require that researchers not put participants in a situation where they might be at risk of harm because of their participation. Harm can be defined as both physical and psychological (Trochim, 2021). A few safeguards should be in place to minimize harm in a research protocol that involves vulnerable participants or sensitive topics.

In compliance of this research with Philippine Data Privacy Law, R.A. No. 10173, known as the "Data Privacy Act of 2012", stated that "The State recognizes the vital role of information and communications technology in nation-building and its inherent obligation to ensure that personal information in information and communications systems in the government and in the private sector are secured and protected." As such, to comply with this act, similarly to compliance with privacy law in the Middle East, the research questions did not identify sensitive information in relation to the respondents.

Furthermore, RA No. 8283, known as the "Intellectual Property Code of the Philippines," states that "It shall protect and secure the exclusive rights of scientists, inventors, artists, and other gifted citizens to their intellectual property and creations, particularly when beneficial to the people, for such periods as provided in this Act. The use of intellectual property bears a social function. To this end, the State shall promote the diffusion of knowledge and information for the promotion of national development and progress and the common good." This act protects the rights of the researcher for "intellectual property rights."

Analytical Schemes

This study used three analytical schemes based on the research objectives: descriptive, comparative, and relational. This research has 13 research objectives.

Objective No. 1 aimed to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, occupational classification, skill level, and length of service. A descriptive-analytical scheme was used.

Objective No. 2 aimed to find out the extent of the OFWs' employment compliance in terms of the following areas: (a) staff qualification, (b) government requirements, and (c) contract requirements. A descriptive-analytical scheme was used.

Objective No. 3 aimed to find out the level of difficulties of OFWs in terms of the following areas: (a) life experience abroad, (b) accommodation, transportation, and safety, and (c) working hours and working conditions. A descriptive-analytical scheme was used.

Objective No. 4 aimed to find out the level of OFWs' job satisfaction in terms of the following areas: (a) compensation, benefits, job security, and tenure, (b) recognition, rewards, and promotions; and (c) professional development opportunities. A descriptive-analytical scheme was used.

Objective No. 5 aimed to find out the extent of OFWs' employment compliance when grouped according to the aforementioned variables. A descriptive-analytical scheme was used.

Objective No. 6 aimed to find out the level of OFWs' difficulties when grouped according to the aforementioned variables. A descriptive-analytical scheme was used.

Objective No. 7 aimed to find out the level of OFWs' job satisfaction when grouped according to the aforementioned variables. A descriptive-analytical scheme was used.

Objective No. 8 aimed to determine whether there was a significant difference in the extent of OFWs' employment compliance when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. A comparative analytical scheme was used.

Objective No. 9 aimed to determine whether there was a significant difference in the level of OFWs' difficulties when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. A comparative analytical scheme was used.

Objective No. 10 aimed to determine whether there was a significant difference in the level of OFWs' job satisfaction when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. A comparative analytical scheme was used.

Objective No. 11 aimed to find out whether there was a significant relationship between the extent of OFWs' employment compliance and the level of OFWs' difficulties. A relational analytical scheme was used.

Objective No. 12 aimed to find out whether there was a significant relationship between the extent of OFWs' employment compliance and the level of OFWs' job satisfaction. A relational analytical scheme was used. And lastly,

Objective No. 13 aimed to find out whether there was a significant relationship between the level of OFWs' difficulties and the level of OFWs' job satisfaction. A relational analytical scheme was used.

Statistical Tools

The data gathered were processed statistically using SPSS. It was statistically analyzed to answer the specific objectives of the study and to test the hypotheses presented in Chapter 1.

Objective No. 1, which determined the profile of the respondents in terms of the variables, the frequency count, and the percentage, will be used.

Frequency count is a measure of the number of times that an event occurs (Veronim M.A. et al., 2019). This was used in counting the number of OFWs as respondents who belong to each category of the variables in their demographic profile. At the same time, a percentage was another way of expressing a proportion. A percentage was equal to the proportion times 100. This was used in converting the frequency into the percentage of the OFWs as respondents who likewise belong to each category of the variables in the demographic profile.

Objective No. 2 Utilized the mean to determine the extent of the OFWs' employment compliance. Areas include (a) staff qualification, (b) government requirements, and (c) contract requirements. According to (Glass, 2017), the mean was considered the most accurate measure of central tendency. The mean was also known as the arithmetic mean and was the most used measure of central tendency.

The interpretation used the following guide:

Mean Score Range	Verbal Interpretations
4.50 – 5.00	Very Great Extent
3.50 – 4.49	Great Extent
2.50 – 3.49	Moderate Extent
1.50 – 2.49	Low Extent
1.00 – 1.49	Very Low Extent

Objective No. 3 Utilized the mean to determine the level of the OFWs' difficulties. Areas include (a) life experience abroad, (b) accommodation, transportation, and safety, and (c) working hours and working conditions.

The interpretation used the following guide:

Mean Score Range	Verbal Interpretations
4.50 – 5.00	Very High Level
3.50 – 4.49	High Level
2.50 – 3.49	Moderate Level
1.50 – 2.49	Low Level
1.00 – 1.49	Very Low Level

Objective No. 4 Utilized the mean to determine the level of the OFWs' job satisfaction. Areas include (a) compensation, benefits, job security, and tenure, (b) recognition, reward, and promotions, and (c) professional development opportunities.

The interpretation used the following guide:

Mean Score Range	Verbal Interpretations
4.50 – 5.00	Very High Level
3.50 – 4.49	High Level
2.50 – 3.49	Moderate Level
1.50 – 2.49	Low Level
1.00 – 1.49	Very Low Level

Objective No. 5 Utilized the mean to determine the extent of OFWs' employment compliance when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 6 Utilized the mean to determine the level of OFWs' difficulties when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 7 Utilized the mean to determine the level of OFWs' job satisfaction when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 8 Used the Mann-Whitney U-Test to determine whether there was a significant difference in the extent of employment compliance of OFWs' when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

The Mann-Whitney U-Test was a non-parametric test used to assess significant differences in a scale or ordinal dependent variable by a single dichotomous independent variable. It was the non-parametric equivalent of the independent samples t-test. This means that the test did not assume any properties regarding the distribution of the dependent variable in the analysis. This made the Mann-Whitney U-test the appropriate analysis to use when analyzing dependent variables on an ordinal scale. According to Bluman (2017), to interpret whether significant differences in the extent of employment compliance, difficulties, and job satisfaction when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables, if the p -value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance (α), then reject the null hypothesis. Accept the null hypothesis if the p -value is greater than 0.05 level of significance (α).

Objective No. 9 Used the Mann-Whitney U-Test to determine whether there was a significant difference in the level of OFWs' difficulties when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 10 Used the Mann-Whitney U-Test to determine whether there was a significant difference in the level of OFWs' job satisfaction when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 11 Used the Spearman Rho at 0.05 significance (α) to find out whether there was a significant relationship between the extent of OFWs' employment compliance and the level of difficulties. Spearman Rho (r), also called Spearman Rank Order Relation Coefficient, was a non-parametric measure of the strength of association that exists between two variables measured on an ordinal scale. The test was used for either ordinal variables or for interval data that has failed the assumptions necessary for conducting Pearson's Product Moment Relation (Blay, 2014). The computed p -values were interpreted using the following guide: significant if the p -value is less than or equal to 0.05 extent of significance (α) and not significant if the p -value is more than 0.05 extent of significance.

Objective No. 12 Used the Spearman Rho at 0.05 significance to find out whether there was a significant relationship between the extent of OFWs' employment compliance and the level of job satisfaction.

Objective No. 13 Used the Spearman Rho at 0.05 significance (α) to find out whether there was a significant relationship between the level of OFWs' difficulties and the level of job satisfaction.

Findings and Discussion:

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the data that were gathered to carry out the pre-determined objectives of this study. It adheres to appropriate procedures consistent with the types of data collected and the methodologies chosen to find answers to each of the problems listed in the introductory chapter. The quantitative data gathered from the respondents' responses to the instrument were tallied, tabulated, and subjected to statistical analysis and interpretation following the objectives of the investigation.

Profile of the respondents in terms of Age, Sex, Occupational Qualification, Skill level, and Length of Service

Table 2 Profile of the Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age	Younger (Below 46 years old)	48	48.00
	Older (46 years old and above)	52	52.00
	Total	100	100.00
Sex	Male	47	47.00
	Female	53	53.00
	Total	100	100.00
Occupational Qualification	Professionals	48	48.00
	Non-Professionals	52	52.00

	Total	100	100.00
Skill Level	Lower (Diploma)	43	43.00
	Higher (Doctorate/Master/Baccalaureate)	57	57.00
	Total	100	100.00
Length of Service	Shorter (Below 14 years)	45	45.00
	Longer (14 years and above)	55	55.00
	Total	100	100.00

Table 2 summarizes the analysis that aimed to determine the profile of the OFWs in terms of age, sex, occupational qualification, skill level, and length of service. In terms of the age of the OFWs' respondents, younger and older were the identified categories. Of the 100 respondents, 48 or 48.00% is younger or below 46 years old, while 52 or 52.00% belongs to 46 years old and above. Sex was biologically categorized as male or female. Male respondents comprised a total of 47 or 47.00%, while 53 or 53.00% are female. The occupational qualification of respondents grouped a total of 48 or 48.00% professionals while 52 or 52.00% non-professionals. The skill level of respondents classified a total of 43 or 43.00% lower skill (Diploma) while 57 or 57.00% higher skill (doctorate, master, and baccalaureate). And for the respondents' length of service, a total of 45 or 45.00% ranged below 14 years (shorter) while 55 or 55.00% ranged 14 years and above (longer) in working abroad.

The profile data indicated that the majority of the OFWs are 46 years old and above, and most respondents were dominated by females. As supported by the finding of Mapa (2020), the ratio of males to females is "45 to 55" in 2019 and "40 to 60" in 2020 for the overall OFWs' abroad; similarly, to this research, the ratio of male to female is "47 to 53" wherein the majority of the OFWs are dominated by females. In terms of the occupational qualification, respondents are dominated by non-professionals with higher skill levels (doctorate, master, and baccalaureate).

According to Mapa (2020), 8.50% is a group of professionals deployed abroad, while the other ratio was distributed to non-professionals that include occupations such as (technicians and associated professionals, clerical support workers, service and sales workers, skilled agriculture forestry and fishery workers, craft and related trade workers, plant and machine operators and assemblers, and elementary occupations). According to Ruiz (2014), through the late 20th century, the largely unregulated Philippine tertiary education system evolved to produce graduates for overseas labor markets. This hands-off, laissez-faire approach to higher education allowed tertiary schools to supply degrees and other educational credentials that Filipinos used to secure overseas employment. Some non-professional occupations were held by Filipino professionals from the Philippines who chose to work abroad as non-professionals due to the good job salaries offered (Ruiz, 2014).

Extent of the OFWs' Employment Compliance in the areas of Staff qualification, Government requirements, and Contract requirements

Table 3
Extent of the OFWs' Employment Compliance in the area of Staff Qualification

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Appropriate education to the type of work.	4.32	Great extent
2. Holding a current and renewed certification/license as per mandated for the job.	3.68	Great extent
3. Updated training in compliance with the work requirements.	3.70	Great extent
4. Equipped with skills needed for a job.	4.47	Great extent
5. Attending seminars and workshops for current trends and practice on the job.	3.39	Moderate extent
Overall mean	3.91	Great extent

Table 3 shows the extent of the OFWs' Employment Compliance in the area of Staff Qualification with an overall mean of 3.91, interpreted as a great extent. Item 4, "It indicates that OFWs were equipped with skills needed for a job," obtained the highest mean of 4.47, interpreted as a great extent, while item number 5, "Attending seminars and workshops for current trends and practice on the job," showed the lowest extent with the mean of 3.39, interpreted as moderate extent. This implies that if the OFWs' employment compliance in the area of staff qualification in attending seminars and workshops for current trends and practices on the job received the lowest mean, this indicates that a sizable portion of OFWs may not be current with the latest practices and trends in their respective fields, perhaps as a result of limited access to opportunities for training and development or other limitations. Additionally, there are difficulties ensuring that these employees comply with training obligations, such as scheduling or accessing training opportunities needing more support or incentives for training attendance.

Finally, it might also have an impact on their employability and future career prospects because companies might favor individuals who are more knowledgeable and up-to-date in their industry. The OFWs' documents upon arrival in the Middle East were checked for compliance with the standards set by the government authority for professional practice. The updated requirement through seminars and workshops was mandatory requirements for professionals (including doctors, nurses, medical technicians, teachers, engineers, architects, etc.), the seminars and workshops involved personal financial expenses by the OFWs'. Organizations offer these seminars with alignment to International Standards with pay.

The mandatory seminars and workshops for health workers, according to Zafra (2018), "Seminars, workshops, trainings were available for medical practitioners such as Basic Life Support (BLS), Advanced Cardiac Life Support (ACLS), Pediatrics Advanced Life Support (PALS), Advanced Trauma Life Support (ATLS), Neonatal Resuscitation Program (NRP) under American Heart Association and Continuing Medical Education (CME) were provided in the Middle East in several accredited training centers." The accreditation of the program was aligned with the American Heart Association, which complied in any part of the Middle Eastern region and in the United States of America.

While for non-professional job workers, it is not mandatory to attend seminars. However, as per the needed update for the job employer provides additional training and education-relevant programs to enhance the job knowledge, skills, and competencies requirements such as Arabic Speaking and Writing Lessons, Computer Lessons, Communication Skills, Fire and Safety, and other competencies required for a job.

Table 4
Extent of the OFWs' Employment Compliance in the area of Government Requirements

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Holding an updated passport duly reported to sponsoring employer.	4.88	Very great extent
2. Holding a renewed expatriate ID consigned by the sponsoring employer from the government.	4.90	Very great extent
3. Updated professional license consigned by government authority.	3.35	Moderate extent
4. OFW is well informed of his contract and government obligations.	4.77	Very great extent
5. OFW knows the Middle Eastern government policies.	4.47	Great extent
Overall mean	4.47	Great extent

Table 4 shows the extent of the OFWs' Employment Compliance in the area of Government Requirements with an overall mean of 4.47, interpreted as a great extent. Item number 2, "Holding a renewed expatriate ID consigned by the sponsoring employer from the government," obtained the highest mean of 4.90, interpreted as a very great extent, while item number 3, "Updated professional license consigned by the government authority," shown the lowest mean of 3.35 interpreted as moderate extent.

This implies that the OFWs comply with the updated government ID provided by the government. The ID system is mandatory for every individual, including expatriates and every citizen of the country in the Middle East. The ID system serves as the primary key to connect to all individuals' transactions. The ID system includes personal identity (biometric and digital through fingerprint system), professional license, driver's license, new vaccination information pertaining to COVID-19, postal address information, passport information, visa information, travel records information, vehicle information, and traffic violations. This government ID is a primary requirement for expatriates and is used in almost all major government and private transactions, such as banks, schools, information, communications technology, etc. An expired government ID without a sponsor can harm every individual living in the Middle East.

While the lowest compliance of OFWs' falls on updated professional licenses. Some OFWs' were professionals from the Philippines, such as teachers, nurses, engineers, electricians, etc. But career changes and working in non-professional jobs caused them to stagnate and have un-renewed licenses.

Table 5
Extent of the OFWs' Employment Compliance in the area of Contract Requirements

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Acceptance of overseas employment contract.	4.90	Very great extent
2. Job Knowledge, able to carry out the assigned job effectively.	4.78	Very great extent
3. Competency, taking responsibility to become efficient in job tools used.	4.60	Very great extent

4. Technical Skills, proficient in demonstrating the job assignment and able to carry out other tasks.	4.66	Very great extent
5. Ability to use constructive feedback to improve performance with new methods.	4.56	Very great extent
Overall mean	4.70	Very great extent

Table 5 shows the extent of the OFWs' Employment Compliance in the area of Contract Requirements with an overall mean of 4.70, interpreted as a very great extent. Item number 1, "Acceptance of overseas employment contract," obtained the highest mean of 4.90, interpreted as a very great extent. However, item number 5, "Ability to use constructive feedback to improve performance with new methods," obtained the lowest mean of 4.56, interpreted as a very great extent.

This implies that the OFWs heartily accepted the overseas employment offered in the Middle East. However, OFWs when they were in the Middle East, their ability to use constructive feedback to improve performance with new methods had an impartial judgment. This OFWs' behavior was observable to avoid conflict on foreign land. In some instances, they follow orders from the higher hierarchy and apply them to work rather than argue what is right or wrong, as long as the job is based on the job description. According to Zafra (2018), "the employment contract is a legal document that binds the employer and employee for specific services, compensation and period of time. The employment contract in the Middle East, particularly the GCC countries, appears in both English and Arabic. The English version is typically written on the left, while the Arabic version is on the right. Make sure that at the end page of the contract, a signature of the employee and employer or representative appears."

Level of OFWs' difficulties in the areas of Life experience abroad, Accommodation, transportation, safety, and Working hours and working conditions

Table 6
Level of OFWs' Difficulties in the area of Life Experience Abroad

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. A good relationship with co-employees and others.	4.79	Very high level
2. Adjustment and tolerance to climate.	4.40	High level
3. The ability to cope with homesickness, anxiety, and stress.	4.39	High level
4. I can keep a reasonable balance between my work and my personal life.	4.53	Very high level
5. Our organization provides us with leisure amenities and recreational activities.	4.07	High level
Overall mean	4.44	High level

Table 6 shows the level of OFWs' difficulties in the area of Life Experience Abroad, with an overall mean of 4.44, interpreted as a high level. Item number 1, "Good relationship with co-employees and others," obtained the highest mean of 4.79, interpreted as a very high level. In contrast, item number 5, "Our organization provides us leisure amenities and recreational activities," obtained the lowest mean of 4.07, interpreted as a high level.

Table 6 provides tolerance evidence of OFWs in response to the difficulties of working abroad. The highest mean implied a good relationship with co-employees and others. Group gatherings organized by individual family groups such as sports groups, wellness, and family groups enable OFWs to reach out to each other and help to cope with homesickness, anxiety, and stress. It can keep a reasonable balance between work and personal life. However, some organizations did not provide leisure amenities and recreational activities, causing burnout of OFWs for the job. Recreational activities help to divert unpleasant situations by turning them into positivity for sustaining working abroad. According to Garabiles et al. (2019), "OFWs are at higher risk of experiencing mental health-related issues such as loneliness, stress, anxiety, depression, and serious mental illness."

Table 7
Level of OFWs' Difficulties in the area of Accommodation, Transportation, and Safety

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Our organization provides us with accommodation or housing allowance.	4.81	Very high level
2. Our accommodation is in a safe environment.	4.75	Very high level

3. Our organization provides transportation or transportation allowance.	4.75	Very high level
4. The workspace in which I work is safe and free from hazards.	4.66	Very high level
5. Our organization updates us on mandated health protocols.	4.84	Very high level
Overall mean	4.76	Very high level

Table 7 shows the level of OFWs' Difficulties in the area of Accommodation, Transportation, and Safety, with an overall mean of 4.76, interpreted as a very high level. Item number 5, "Our organization updates us on mandated health protocols," obtained the highest mean of 4.84, interpreted as a very high level. In contrast, item number 4, "The workspace in which I work is safe and free from hazards," obtained the lowest mean of 4.66, interpreted as a very high level. This implies that in the Middle East, all organizations follow the rules and obligations mandated by the government to update every individual employee on mandated health protocols. Health protocol, particularly in the COVID-19 situation, wherein all are compulsory to receive vaccine except for those with allergies that require physicians' clearance and the observable situation in case of induction of the vaccine. Also, health protocols on HIV, AIDS, and other contagious diseases were strictly implemented for re-testing upon renewal of work contracts, particularly for food services jobs and healthcare providers.

However, the lowest mean response on item number 4 signifies that working abroad includes risk. This includes the workspace in which OFWs work safely and free from hazards. OFWs working in hospitals, industrial cities of chemicals or pharmaceuticals, heavy equipment, building constructions, etc., have risks. But then the organizations provide safety education and training on handling such jobs.

Table 8

Level of OFWs' Difficulties in the area of Working Hours and Working Conditions

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Our working hours are reasonable on employee capability & productivity.	4.54	Very high level
2. Employees work overtime with pay.	4.59	Very high level
3. I have adequate days off in a week.	4.53	Very high level
4. My workload is reasonable.	4.33	High level
5. Adequate equipment and supplies are available for the work.	4.43	High level
Overall mean	4.48	High level

Table 8 shows the level of OFWs' difficulties in the area of working hours and working conditions, with an overall mean of 4.48, interpreted as a high level. Item number 2, "Employee work overtime with pay," obtained the highest mean of 4.59, interpreted as a very high level. In contrast, item 4, "My workload is reasonable," obtained the lowest mean of 4.33, interpreted as a high level. This implies that OFWs in the Middle East received an extrinsic motivation wherein the overtime was paid calculated as 150% of their regular daily salary. However, the lowest mean implied dissatisfaction with the workload. In some instances, job overload was observed, causing burnout.

Generally, the working hours and working conditions. According to Richter et al. (2014), working hours and working conditions refer to actual working time with long working hours, high workload, and a critical amount of sleep deprivation can be listed among quantitative job demands positively associated with a high risk of stress and burnout. Examples of quantitative job demands related to stress and burnout include role conflicts and emotionally demanding situations in the workplace. Furthermore, the absence of certain resources, such as the lack of control, social support, or autonomy in the job, is also linked to burnout. (Chemali et al., 2019) described burnout as a syndrome characterized by emotional exhaustion, depression, and a diminished sense of personal achievement. According to Richter et al. (2014), some demographic variables associated link with burnout include several health scenarios reported on high rates of sick leave and absenteeism, and job turnover. Also, symptoms of burnout are significant risk markers for early retirement because of work disability.

Unveiling working conditions of some organizations in the Middle East, according to (Chemali et al., 2019), doctors, nurses, and other healthcare professionals working in private hospitals experienced long working hours. Duties used to be excessively long, with commonly 30 hours extra during the week and more than 80 hours at the weekend. According to Dessiye & Emirie (2018), some non-professional employees in the Middle East working as service crew oriented in hotels, 24/7 convenient coffee shops experienced long working hours with overtime pay for a maximum of 12 hours daily and night shift duty every day with only 1 day off per month. Furthermore, according to (Ivers, 2017), non-professionals employee working in the construction industry was at risk, including work pressures and time-saving

benefit caused by unrealistic schedule. In the advent of Ramadan, regular working hours of a Sunday to Thursday schedule are arranged as 10:00 am – 04:00 pm for Muslims and 08:00 am to 05:00 pm for non-Muslims (regular working hours). However, according to Mellahi & Al-Hinai (2012), working hours and conditions are highly favorable for clerical workers, teachers, and other office workers. Working hours only from 7 am to 4 pm or 8 am to 5 pm with one (1) day off per week for private and two (2) days off per week for government organizations.

Level of OFWs' job satisfaction in the areas of Compensation, Benefits, Job Security and Tenure, Recognition, reward, promotions, and Professional development opportunities

Table 9

Level of OFWs' Job Satisfaction in the area of Compensation, Benefits, Job Security and Tenure

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. My salary is appropriate for the position and qualifications I hold.	4.04	High level
2. I am satisfied with my medical and leave benefits.	4.42	High level
3. I have a round-trip ticket paid for by my employer for mid-year or annual leave.	4.86	Very high level
4. Working as OFW provides job security.	4.30	High level
5. I am grateful for giving me a chance to work in the Middle East.	4.84	Very high level
Overall mean	4.49	Very high level

Table 9 shows the level of OFWs' Job Satisfaction in the area of Compensation, Benefits, Job Security, and Tenure, with an overall mean of 4.49, interpreted as a very high level. Item number 3, "I have a round-trip ticket paid by my employer for mid-year or annual leave," obtained the highest mean of 4.86, interpreted as a very high level. In contrast, item number 1, "My salary is appropriate to the position and qualification I hold," obtained the lowest mean of 4.04, interpreted as a high level. This implies that the satisfaction of OFWs was provided with round-trip tickets from the point of origin in Manila, Philippines, for international flights upon contract. Some organizations have two round-trip tickets per year, others once a year, and the longer contract was one round-trip ticket every two years. Few organizations provide local transit from Manila to regional locations for local tickets provided by the organization. However, OFWs are dissatisfied with their salary in comparison to the appropriateness of the position they hold. Far Eastern (particularly Filipino) was one of the other Far Eastern countries with the lowest-paid nationality in the Middle East. The salary grading in the Middle East was commonly based on Nationality or the passport held by an employee. The value of salary varies depending on the economic situation of the country. The Philippines belongs to the countries that are employed abroad with the lowest labor cost in the global human resource market, particularly in the Middle East.

According to Kang & Lee (2021), the area of Human Resource Management (HRM) in the employee compensation system could lead to benefits. The compensation that is important for both individual employees and the organization is one of the highest costs for an organization. Compensation may be critical for the success or failure of an organization, and the characteristics of the workers and their interactions form the basis for strategic planning and implementation. Also, compensation schemes should be driven by policy, structure, employee engagement, and work as an integral part of HR (Human Resources). However, among academics, there appears to be disagreement regarding where pay-for-performance programs in which there is a direct relationship between an employee's performance results and their compensation reward should be used in organizations as a compensation strategy to enhance organizational performance or whether they are inherently ineffective or even counterproductive in that role. Furthermore, the compensation scheme contrasts with "skill-based pay" (SBP) and "pay-for-knowledge." The SBP system states that employees are compensated with additional wages in return for formal certification of the mastery of credentials, expertise, and skills. Expertise in performing tasks is obtained and can be seen. Knowledge can be thought of as acquired information used in tasks, while competencies can be defined as more normal skills or traits needed to perform tasks, often in multiple roles or jobs. Also, employee compensation is related to employee competency.

Table 10

Level of OFWs' Job Satisfaction in the area of Recognition, Reward, and Promotions

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. I receive recognition for a job well done.	3.69	High level
2. I receive incentives for my good job performance.	3.07	Moderate level

3. I received a certificate of praise for my good performance.	3.20	Moderate level
4. There are opportunities for promotion in my organization.	2.75	Moderate level
5. I receive a salary increase merit upon my contract renewal.	3.70	High level
Overall mean	3.28	Moderate level

Table 10 shows the level of OFWs' Job Satisfaction in the area of Recognition, Reward, and Promotions, with an overall mean of 3.28, interpreted as a moderate level. Item number 5, "I receive salary increase merit upon my contract renewal," obtained the highest mean of 3.70, interpreted as a high level. Item number 4, "There are opportunities for promotion in my organization," obtained the lowest mean of 2.75, interpreted as a moderate level.

This implies that OFWs receive salary increase merit upon renewal of the contract. The salary benefits and recognition of jobs varied on the performance of the employees as a basis for provisioning salary increases as merit. Employees would be more driven if their bosses recognized them (Pancasila et al., 2020).

However, the lowest mean provides moderate responses from the respondents. This implies due to the localization process, employee promotion for expatriate employees has been suppressed or suspended.

Recognizing workers' contributions entails valuing and thinking about their contributions (Ali & Anwar, 2021). According to Akafo & Boateng (2015), rewards and recognition play an imperative role in motivating employees and improving performance. Organizations are also developing more complex recognition programs which focus on non-monetary rewards for employees, such as the employee-of-the-month program. A reward is something given or received in return or recompense for service, merit, hardship, etc. Some theorists also refer to reward as compensation. Compensation rewards people for performing organizational work through pay, incentives, and benefits. Rewards can be extrinsic and intrinsic. Intrinsic rewards often include praise for completing a project or meeting performance objectives. Extrinsic rewards are tangible and take both monetary and nonmonetary forms (ibid). Tangible compensation may be direct or indirect. With direct forms of compensation, the employer exchanges monetary rewards for work done. Indirect compensation is given to every employee because of organizational membership.

Conclusion:

Overseas Filipino Workers (OFWs) are international investments in human capital and should be regarded as one of the major stakeholders in the Philippines' national development economy. They are professionals, and Non-Professionals who obtained their training and education from the Philippines in different colleges, universities, and Technical Schools with global competitive excellent human skills, knowledge, abilities, and other characteristics (KSAOs). Becoming an OFW requires courage and strong determination to leave the country to work abroad, carrying the composure of being a diligent Filipino worker.

OFWs' complied with different human capital requirements for staff qualifications, government requirements, and contract requirements. Aligned current knowledge, skills, abilities, and other characteristics required globally, particularly in the Middle East, as the respondents of this study.

Working abroad has difficulties, commonly life experiences encountered, prone to a high risk of experiencing mental health-related issues such as loneliness, stress, anxiety, depression, and serious mental illness. This research proved that OFWs' in the Middle East were able to handle these difficulties. However, only the dissatisfaction pertaining to amenities and recreational activities was a minor concern. This help OFWs' to maintain a healthy life balance between work and personal life.

OFWs' in the Middle East were provided with accommodation, transportation, and security for their safety by their employer. They were updated with the government's mandatory health protocols. Generally, OFWs' were able to cope with the working hours and working conditions. Non-professionals working in offices, including teachers, instructors, and professors, researchers, librarians, laboratory staff working in academe, enjoyed the regular working hours and conditions due to the flexibility of working time. However, some organizations where the nature of the job was service-oriented experience overload and long working hours, causing emotional exhaustion, depression, and a diminished sense of personal achievement. This burnout was experienced by some professionals, medical professionals (doctors, nurses, and other health workers.) This burnout was also experienced by those working in some 24/7 convenience shops like coffee shops, hotels, and others.

With regard to compensation, benefits, job security, and tenure, OFWs were very satisfied and grateful for the opportunity and chance to work in the Middle East. They have a round-trip ticket provided by their employer upon

renewal of the contract. However, some wanted more than the salary appropriate to their position and qualification, as well as their medical and leave benefits. They believe that working as OFWs' provides no guarantee of job security. On recognition, reward, and promotions, this extrinsic motivation satisfier was commonly provided to the locals for them to experience leadership growth and on the call for localization for sustainable local empowerment purposes. Furthermore, OFWs' believe that they grow holistically in the organization they belong to; they have the opportunity to learn and grow and establish career growth. However, opportunities for training and continuing education were on the status quo for some, and with that, the opportunity to act up in a higher position stagnated.

Staff Qualification provides significant comparative results in terms of age between younger and older; younger OFWs have more room to improve themselves on innovation pertaining to the job they hold. Younger OFWs are considered to be more vibrant pertaining to manpower skills. Older OFWs were vulnerable to the replacement of locals in localization policy in the Middle East. The Older OFWs were turning their heads to the Philippines as returning OFWs. Older OFWs find it hard to re-integrate into the Philippine manpower; instead, to think of early retirement or entrepreneurship, in some instances thinking of crossing countries to spend their older age due to some security and healthcare benefits offered in other countries. In terms of occupational qualification between professionals and non-professionals. Professionals may be able to find a new job in the Philippines as returning OFWs due to the priority lane program of DMW for the re-integration program. However, Non-Professionals suffered and found it hard to seek a new job in the Philippines. Some instances offered other employment in different countries with bilateral employment agreements from the Philippines. Furthermore, this study finds no significant on sex, skill level, and length of service as a response by the respondents.

Government requirements provide comparative significance in terms of occupational qualification for professionals and non-professionals. Currently, most non-professional jobs held by OFWs are vulnerable to replacement by locals. Occupational qualification was the primary basis of the Middle East in analyzing the ratio of employment opportunities between expatriates and locals, wherein the ratio should be 30% expatriate and 70% locals in Saudi Arabia as the first country to implement a rigorous localization program. Women empowerment was also part of this change in international human resource management in the Middle East. The newly graduated locals could hold the job, or any non-professional locals able to handle the job through internship and training, after which a turnover opportunity was given to replace the expatriates. Age, Sex, Skill Level, and Length of Service were not significant.

Contract requirement, Life Experience Abroad, Accommodation, and Safety provides no comparative significance in terms of variables of this study.

Working hours and working conditions provide comparative significance in terms of Age and Occupational Qualification. Not significant in variable Sex, Skill Level, and Length of Service. Older age OFWs were vulnerable to replacement by younger age locals. However, younger age locals find difficulty handling long working hours compared to older OFWs. Despite younger age, locals were trained by Older OFWs to adapt to the job situation as mandated. This can be seen in the turnover process of the job by Older OFWs to the Younger locals.

Compensation, Benefits, Job Security, and Tenure provide comparative significance in terms of Age, Occupational Qualification, Skill Level, and Length of Service. Salaries in the Middle East were less than compared to other countries. Benefits in the Middle East were good; OFWs were provided with health insurance, round-trip airplane tickets upon renewal of contract, provided with accommodation or housing allowance, annual leave or mid-year leave, and paid overtime as per needed. Working as an OFW provides no job security, as responded by male respondents. Comparative in terms of age, younger OFWs have more rooms to improve compared with Older OFWs. Compared in terms of Occupational Qualification, Older OFWs were more qualified and gained more experience when compared to younger ones. Compared to Skill Level, Higher Skill Level can provide more comprehensive details relating to jobs when compared to Lower Skills. In terms of Length of Services, Longer Services gained more experience compared to Shorter Services. However, not significant in terms of Sex.

Recognition, Reward, Promotions, and Professional Development Opportunities provide comparative no significance in terms of variables of this study. However, attending seminars, workshops, and even attending formal educational classes was the problem of the OFWs in the Middle East for both younger and older age, and professionals and non-professionals.

This study hypothesized that the extent of OFWs' employment compliance could influence the level of difficulties. It was also hypothesized that the extent of employment compliance could influence their level of job satisfaction. In like manner, the level of OFWs' difficulties could influence their level of job satisfaction. This hypothesis was accepted. To conclude the hypotheses, the extent of the OFWs' Employment Compliance in relation to the level of Difficulties was significant. The extent of employment Compliance in relation to the level of Job Satisfaction was significant. And the level of Difficulties in relation to Job Satisfaction was significant. Dependent and Independent variables rely on each other as part of a whole package for OFWs' working in the Middle East.

The impact of this study is to strengthen the manpower capabilities of current and aspiring OFWs through re-training on current innovation globally and ensuring the cost of labor will be worth turning their heads to the Middle East. While the Middle East was raising their bar higher in terms of manpower compliance, this call to the Philippine labor to enhance and raise the bar higher too of current manpower of the Filipino to align with the current demand labor globally for the Filipino labor to be equipped of current practices on labor market demand that led to equitable to cost value of qualifications and expertise. Also, for the government to look after the situation of current OFWs in the Middle East and the extent of support for the returning OFWs affected by localization policy by reviewing the provisioned programs for professionals and non-professionals whose heading their heads to return to their home country, the Philippines.

Limitations and Further Research:

In the light of the findings and conclusions derived from the study, the following recommendations and plans of action are hereby formulated:

1. To enhance the OFWs' Employment Compliance to work in the Middle East, the authority designated by the Philippine government ensure to disseminate to all OFWs in the Middle East of the new rules, policies, and regulations (e.g., Localization policy such as Saudization, Qatarization, Omanization, etc.) pertaining to the current situation on employment compliance. This is to alert current and aspiring OFWs' who want to work in the Middle East.
2. The Philippine government should help OFWs to align current practices, knowledge, skills, and competencies to global human resource needs. This can be done through the development of the higher education sector, including technical schools.
3. Strengthen the OFWs to be able to handle a good relationship with co-employees through inclusive seminars provided by the government and promoting leisure and recreational activities to handle stress and loneliness.
4. Strengthening the compulsory contribution for SSS and PAG-IBIG Fund, PhilHealth, aside from the OWWA insurance for OFWs, so that when they end work overseas, they can still have the privilege to avail the services of the said agencies upon returning to the Philippines, returning OFWs.
5. Both local and national governments must therefore work together to develop and implement a comprehensive program that would create employment opportunities for repatriated, displaced, and end-contracted or returning OFWs, both for professionals and non-professionals, to ensure the continuity of employment opportunities for returning OFWs. These include the strengthening of the current reintegration program for giving priority for employment to returning OFWs'. Also, to strengthen the current entrepreneurial support for the returning OFWs' whose goal was to become independent or group entrepreneurs (Fernandez et al., 2020).
6. The national government must step in, not just in the form of programs like Balik Probinsya or Hatid Tulong but more towards comprehensive and sustainable support and employment package (Fernandez et al., 2020).
7. COVID-19 educates people to understand the essential part needed by humanity to sustain life. Survival requires human knowledge, skills, abilities, and other human behaviors (KSAOs) in adopting the new challenge of the dynamic environment. OFWs were among the affected workforce to sustain employment abroad, at the same time protecting themselves from the threats to health and safety. In relation to human resource management, according to Collings et al. (2021), "the key challenge for organizations in pivoting to helping employees work from involved salvaging business continuity. This required a substantive digital transformation as organizations redesigned technology and work process to perform tasks virtually, often for the first time, in addition to reskilling and upskilling employees." In this sense, it is highly recommended that new skills should be retrained to OFWs in sustaining employment abroad and locally.
8. Adoption of the Transformational Higher Education Systems by developing local advancement in technology educational skills to benchmark or exceed the bar higher set as expectations in the global human resource market. It includes developing a higher education and technical education curriculum that can prepare graduates for jobs and technologies that don't exist to solve problems that we still need to learn are problems. To strengthen the readiness of the workforce after graduation, it is highly recommended to ensure a skills framework aligned with the 21st Century themes focusing on global awareness, finance, economics, business and entrepreneurial literacy, civic literacy, and health literacy by strengthening subject matter with real life situation on native language reading and writing, world language reading and writing including English and nearby country to exchange communication and ideas efficiently, arts with a focus on native and promoting it globally, geography including navigation and terrestrial, history by preserving local the past story how they survive and able to sustain life that may be useful in current society, mathematics to help scientifically analyze and evaluate the measure of facts that create impact, science to develop innovation, government/civic to enhance political well and understanding of leadership. Ensure to develop learning and innovation skills with critical thinking, problem-solving skills, creativity and innovation, communication, and collaboration. Develop learning on information, media, and technology skills with a focus on information Literacy, media literacy, and ICT literacy. And lastly, inject all learners to prepare themselves for life and career skills with special features on flexibility and adaptability, initiative and self-directed, social and cross-cultural skills, productivity and accountability, and leadership and responsibility.

- The Philippine Government should allocate more to the sustainable developmental program for human resource management for local employment to economic situations by developing more jobs and by aligning educational institutions to provide local jobs with benchmarks on international or global standards. In that sense, less surplus human skills shall be needed for exporting them (OFWs) and become useful in other developed countries instead of holding them in their own homeland for the availability of sustainable employment for the Filipinos.

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